

UrbanIneq: an open framework for urban accessibility datasets with potential socio-spatial inequality patterns

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Abstract

Urban planning increasingly relies on data-driven approaches to support decision-making. However, the growing adoption of computational and machine learning methods in urban contexts also raises important concerns regarding the reproduction and amplification of existing socio-spatial inequalities, particularly when datasets contain historical biases affecting vulnerable population groups. At the same time, openly accessible and harmonized urban datasets integrating socioeconomic information with spatial accessibility indicators remain scarce in the literature, hindering reproducible urban accessibility and socio-spatial inequality studies.

This paper presents UrbanIneq, an open-source platform designed for the automated retrieval, integration, and analysis of urban datasets across municipalities in Andalusia, Spain. The framework combines publicly available spatial and socioeconomic data with GIS-based accessibility measures to Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCF) at census-section level. UrbanIneq integrates R-based geospatial analysis, a Python FastAPI backend, and a React-based web interface within a fully reproducible and containerized workflow. By providing harmonized and research-ready urban datasets through an interoperable infrastructure, the platform is intended to support researchers and policy makers in the analysis of urban inequalities affecting disadvantaged population groups.

Keywords: Socio-spatial inequalities, Open urban data, Urban analytics, Accessibility,

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1. Introduction

Numerous studies in the urban planning literature have documented multiple forms of urban inequality that disadvantage individuals according to race, gender, age, family structure, immigration status or income level, see Fainstein (2010). Such inequalities often result in vulnerable groups experiencing limited access to healthcare services, educational facilities, green spaces, and other urban amenities, see Gilderbloom and Rosentraub (1990), Koprowska et al. (2020), Kim et al. (2022), Shahraki (2021) or Wang et al. (2022). Equity in urban planning is closely associated with fair access to urban resources, services, and opportunities, and planning interventions are generally considered equitable when they reduce disadvantages affecting minorities and vulnerable populations (Loh and Kim, 2021).

On the other hand, in recent years, urban planning has increasingly relied on urban analytics and data-driven approaches supported by advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence (Koenig et al., 2020; Singleton et al., 2022). Large-scale urban datasets are now routinely used to support decision-making processes related to mobility, land use, public services, environmental sustainability, and urban accessibility, see Engin et al. (2020), Bibri (2023), Bokolo (2023). However, when urban planning decision-making relies on data-driven models trained on historically biased data, existing inequalities affecting vulnerable groups may be reproduced or even amplified, Mehrabi et al. (2021). Kontokosta and Hong (2021) provides a clear example of this phenomenon in the urban context by showing how socio-spatial disparities in datasets can bias smart-city decision-making. These concerns are closely related to the notion of fairness in machine learning, a rapidly growing research area broadly concerned with preventing prediction models from reproducing social biases, see Oneto and Chiappa (2020); Caton and Haas (2024); Mehrabi et al. (2021); Carrizosa et al. (2024).

Most fairness-related benchmark datasets and methodological frameworks have been developed in domains such as finance, criminal justice, healthcare, education, or online recom-

mendation systems, see Le Quy et al. (2022). By contrast, publicly available and harmonized urban datasets suitable for analysing accessibility disparities and potential spatial biases remain scarce. Several challenges hinder access to urban data for fairness-related analyses. First, urban information is typically fragmented across multiple institutional repositories containing heterogeneous spatial formats and data structures. Second, temporal inconsistencies frequently arise because the available sources often differ in reference years and update cycles. In addition, preparing research-ready datasets usually requires substantial preprocessing efforts involving geospatial analysis and data cleaning and integration. Reproducibility also remains problematic, as many urban-data workflows rely on manual integration and processing steps that are difficult to document and replicate. Finally, analyses at fine spatial scales, such as census-section level, introduce computational challenges due to the large number of geometries and routing operations involved. Altogether, these limitations constitute a significant technical challenge to accessing urban datasets suitable for identifying potential inequalities and accessibility disparities affecting vulnerable population groups. As a consequence, they also hinder the development of fairness-oriented methodologies aimed at detecting and mitigating spatial biases and unequal outcomes in urban contexts, an issue that recent literature has highlighted as increasingly important, see Janowicz (2023), Singleton and Spielman (2026) or Saxena et al. (2024).

To overcome the commented limitations, this paper introduces UrbanIneq, a software platform aimed at simplifying the acquisition and preparation of urban datasets for accessibility and inequality studies across municipalities in Andalusia (Spain). The generated datasets currently cover the 785 municipalities composing the Andalusian region, providing accessibility and socioeconomic information across highly diverse urban and territorial contexts. Andalusia constitutes an especially relevant case study for urban accessibility research due to the coexistence of densely populated metropolitan areas such as Seville or Málaga, medium-sized cities as Cádiz or Almería, coastal municipalities, for example, Marbella or Algeciras, rural or mountain settlements such as Grazalema or Cazorla, as well as territories exhibiting

substantial socioeconomic inequalities and demographic contrasts. The system automatically gathers information from multiple public repositories, integrates spatial and socioeconomic variables, and computes walking-distance accessibility indicators associated with Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCF), two urban services frequently examined in the literature on accessibility disparities, see Koprowska et al. (2020), Kim et al. (2022), Semenzato et al. (2023), Zhang and Chen (2024), Williams et al. (2023), Fiscella and Williams (2004), Northridge et al. (2011). The resulting datasets are structured to facilitate quantitative analyses of accessibility conditions across different population groups. In addition to generating accessibility-oriented urban datasets, UrbanIneq provides a reproducible open urban data science infrastructure integrating heterogeneous spatial, socioeconomic, and routing-based information sources within a unified computational workflow. The platform combines automated geospatial preprocessing, accessibility computation through routing services, harmonized census-tract dataset generation, reusable spatial outputs, and a web-based exploratory interface within an interoperable microservices architecture. By facilitating the automated integration of open urban data sources, UrbanIneq supports future research on accessibility disparities, socio-spatial inequalities, and fairness-aware urban analytics. It is important to emphasize that UrbanIneq is not itself a fairness-correction framework, but rather an open data and accessibility infrastructure designed to support subsequent fairness-oriented analyses. To the best of our knowledge, publicly available and reproducible urban accessibility frameworks integrating harmonized socioeconomic and routing-based accessibility information at census-tract level remain limited in the literature.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the urban datasets generated by UrbanIneq, including the public data sources, the integrated socioeconomic attributes, and the accessibility indicators associated with Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCF). Section 3.2 presents the UrbanIneq software architecture and the automated workflow used for urban data retrieval, harmonization, accessibility computation, and exploratory disparity analysis. Section 4 illustrates the capabilities of the framework through two case

studies conducted in Andalusian municipalities, focusing on accessibility analyses related to UGS and HCF. Finally, Section 5 discusses the main contributions, limitations, and future extensions of the framework in the context of open urban data science, reproducible accessibility research, and equity-oriented urban analytics.

2. Urban dataset description

This section describes the main components of the datasets generated by UrbanIneq. First, we present the public data sources used to retrieve socioeconomic and spatial information for municipalities across Andalusia (Spain), together with the walking-distance accessibility measures computed for Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCF). Finally, we describe the structure of the resulting harmonized datasets and their associated spatial information at census-section level.

2.1. Data sources and spatial coverage

UrbanIneq integrates information from five main public data sources combining spatial, socioeconomic, demographic, and network data for municipalities across Andalusia (Spain).

IECA Spatial Reference Data (DERA)

The Andalusian Institute of Statistics and Cartography (*Instituto Andaluz de Estadística y Cartografía*, IECA) maintains the Spatial Reference Data of Andalusia (*Datos Espaciales de Referencia de Andalucía*, DERA), a public geospatial repository containing administrative boundaries, urban services, and territorial infrastructure layers.¹ In particular, UrbanIneq uses municipal boundaries, census tract boundaries, urban green, outpatient healthcare centers, and hospitals or specialized healthcare facilities. The data are distributed as ESRI shapefiles using the ETRS89 coordinate reference system (EPSG:25830).

¹<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/institutodeestadisticaycartografia/dega/datos-espaciales-de-referencia-de-andalucia-dera>

IECA Demographic and Socioeconomic Indicators (IEPABRA)

UrbanIneq also incorporates the Statistical Indicators of Andalusia’s Population Based on Administrative Records (IEPABRA), provided by IECA.² This source contains census tract-level indicators related to demographic structure, household composition, poverty, and material deprivation. The spatial format of the data preserves the geographic dimension of socioeconomic variation across urban areas.

INE Household Income Distribution Atlas (ADRH)

The National Statistics Institute of Spain (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, INE) provides the Household Income Distribution Atlas (*Atlas de Distribución de Renta de los Hogares, ADRH*).³ This dataset contains income-related indicators at multiple territorial scales, including mean and median household income, income per person and employment indicators. The information is distributed in tabular format.

INE Population and Housing Census

The 2021 Population and Housing Census constitutes the most recent complete census operation conducted by INE.⁴ UrbanIneq uses census tract-level attributes related to total population, age structure, nationality, employment status, and household composition.

OpenStreetMap Network Data (Geofabrik Extract)

Street-network data are obtained from the Andalusian OpenStreetMap extract distributed by Geofabrik.⁵ These data include road topology, pedestrian pathways, and routing-related attributes used to compute walking-distance accessibility measures through the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM).

An important issue concerns temporal harmonization across data sources. Although some

²<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/institutodeestadisticaycartografia/dega/estadisticas-de-poblacion-de-andalucia-basadas-en-registros-administrativos-epabra>

³https://www.ine.es/componentes_inebase/ADRH_total_nacional.htm

⁴<https://www.ine.es/censos2021/>

⁵<https://download.geofabrik.de/europe/spain/andalucia.html>

of the considered repositories provide more recent information, UrbanIneq uses 2021 as the main reference year because it corresponds to the most recent complete Population and Housing Census conducted by the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE). Using 2021 as a common temporal reference facilitates the consistent integration of spatial, demographic, and socioeconomic information across municipalities in Andalusia.

2.2. Socioeconomic attributes and accessibility measures

This subsection describes the socioeconomic attributes and accessibility indicators generated by UrbanIneq for the analysis of accessibility disparities across municipalities in Andalusia at census tract level.

Socioeconomic attributes

UrbanIneq integrates a set of socioeconomic attributes obtained from the INE and IECA data sources described in Section 2.1. Within the platform, these variables may be considered *sensitive attributes*, since they characterize population groups potentially exposed to unequal accessibility conditions across urban census tracts. In particular, the framework incorporates the following census-tract-level attributes:

X_1 : Total population, obtained from the INE Population and Housing Census.

X_2 : Average net household income, obtained from the Household Income Distribution Atlas (ADRH).

X_3 : Underage population, defined as the percentage of residents younger than 18 years old, obtained from IEPABRA.

X_4 : Elderly population, defined as the percentage of residents older than 64 years old, obtained from the INE Population and Housing Census.

X_5 : Unemployment rate, defined as the percentage of unemployed individuals with respect to the total active population, obtained from the INE Population and Housing Census.

X_6 : Foreign population, defined as the percentage of residents without Spanish citizenship with respect to the total population, obtained from the INE Population and Housing Census.

X_7 : Loneliness index, defined as the percentage of elderly residents older than 64 years old living alone with respect to the total elderly population, obtained from IEPABRA.

Accessibility indicators

In addition to socioeconomic information, UrbanIneq computes network-based walking-distance accessibility indicators associated with Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCF). In this work, these urban services are defined as follows:

UGS: Publicly accessible urban green areas primarily intended for recreation, leisure, and outdoor social activities.

HCF: Healthcare-related urban services including primary healthcare centers, hospitals, and specialized medical facilities, considering both public and private institutions.

Accessibility indicators for both UGS and HCF are computed as the minimum, average, and maximum walking distances between the centroid of each census tract and the centroids of the corresponding urban services. Distances are calculated over the OpenStreetMap street network described in Section 2.1 using the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM).

Minimum and average walking-distance measures are widely used and conceptually meaningful indicators of urban accessibility. In particular, minimum walking distance captures immediate proximity to the nearest urban service and is frequently employed in studies on accessibility to parks, healthcare facilities, and everyday urban amenities because it reflects basic access conditions and potential spatial exclusion patterns (Apparicio et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2021). By contrast, average walking distance provides a more global characterization of accessibility conditions, reflecting the relative centrality or peripheralization of urban areas with respect to the overall spatial distribution of opportunities (Porta et al., 2006).

The maximum walking distance complements these indicators by capturing potential situations of spatial isolation and the worst-case accessibility cost within the urban service system (Rad and Alimohammadi, 2021; Ribeiro et al., 2021). The joint computation of minimum, average, and maximum walking-distance indicators therefore enables a multidimensional characterization of urban accessibility conditions, consistent with recent studies arguing that no single metric can fully capture the complexity of urban accessibility patterns (Semenzato et al., 2023; Battiston and Schifanella, 2024; Zhang and Chen, 2024).

Spatial preprocessing considerations

Accessibility indicators are computed using the geometric centroid of each census tract polygon. Nevertheless, for large or spatially irregular tracts, researchers may optionally replace these centroids with alternative representative locations better reflecting actual population concentration patterns. Figure 1 illustrates this adjustment procedure for the city of Seville. Similarly, certain census tracts may be excluded from the analysis when they do not adequately represent residential urban environments, for example in the presence of industrial zones, restricted areas, or sparsely populated peripheral land. Figure 2 illustrates this preprocessing operation for the city of Jerez de la Frontera (Cádiz), where peripheral industrial census tracts are excluded in order to focus the accessibility analysis on residential urban areas.

The configuration commands used for centroid adjustment and tract exclusion in these examples are provided in Appendix A. Both preprocessing operations are optional and may be defined by researchers according to the objectives and spatial characteristics of the study area. When such preprocessing adjustments are introduced, the accessibility workflow must be re-executed in order to regenerate the corresponding accessibility indicators, visualizations, and output datasets.

2.3. Output datasets

UrbanIneq generates standardized RDS datasets integrating socioeconomic attributes, accessibility indicators, spatial layers, and auxiliary objects intended to facilitate subsequent

(a) Original geometric centroids.

(b) Adjusted centroids.

Figure 1: Illustration of centroid adjustment in Seville. For large or spatially irregular peripheral census tracts, geometric centroids may be replaced by representative points better aligned with actual residential settlement patterns.

statistical and geospatial analyses. Additional technical details regarding the structure of the generated objects are provided in Appendix B.

In addition to the RDS dataset, the platform also generates visual outputs including maps of census tracts, Urban Green Spaces, Healthcare Facilities, accessibility indicators, and selected socioeconomic attributes. The complete output package is additionally provided as a compressed ZIP file to facilitate download and reproducibility.

Figure 2: Example of census-tract exclusion in Jerez de la Frontera.

3. UrbanIneq workflow and accessibility analysis

3.1. Software architecture

UrbanIneq follows a containerized microservices architecture designed to support reproducible urban-data processing and accessibility analysis workflows. The system is composed of four main components responsible for routing computations, geospatial processing, workflow orchestration, and user interaction. Figure 3 illustrates the overall architecture of the platform and the interactions between its main software services.

The routing component is based on the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM), which performs walking-distance calculations over OpenStreetMap street-network data for municipalities across Andalusia. Geospatial processing and data integration tasks are implemented through an R-based service responsible for data retrieval, preprocessing, harmonization, ac-

Figure 3: UrbanIneq system architecture. The platform integrates routing services, geospatial processing modules, and a web-based interface to generate accessibility indicators, spatial datasets, and visualization outputs from multiple public urban-data repositories.

cessibility computation, and dataset generation. Workflow orchestration and communication between services are managed through a FastAPI layer, while the user interface provides interactive access to municipality selection, accessibility configuration, visualization outputs, and dataset download functionalities.

Additional implementation and deployment details are provided in Appendix D.

3.2. Data processing workflow

UrbanIneq implements an automated workflow for retrieving, harmonizing, and processing urban datasets from multiple public sources. As previously described, the workflow integrates socioeconomic, demographic, spatial, and street-network data in order to generate accessibility indicators and research-ready urban datasets at census-tract level.

The processing pipeline consists of four main stages. First, spatial and socioeconomic information is retrieved from the institutional repositories described in Section 2.1. Second, the retrieved datasets are harmonized and preprocessed to ensure spatial consistency across sources, including coordinate-system alignment, census-tract matching, and centroid computation. If required by the characteristics of the study area, researchers may additionally perform

manual preprocessing operations on the original spatial data, such as centroid replacement or census-tract exclusion, before re-executing the accessibility workflow. Third, accessibility indicators are computed through the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) using walking distances over the OpenStreetMap street network. Finally, the generated information is consolidated into standardized accessibility datasets and visualization outputs suitable for statistical and geospatial analyses.

Figure 4 illustrates several components of the UrbanIneq graphical interface used to configure and execute the accessibility-data generation workflow, including municipality selection and accessibility-distance configuration.

Figure 4: Graphical user interface of the UrbanIneq platform.

Additional implementation details regarding the internal processing modules and workflow scripts are provided in Appendix E.

3.3. Accessibility disparity analysis

This stage computes exploratory summary measures aimed at quantifying accessibility disparities between sensitive and non-sensitive census-tract groups derived from a selected socioeconomic attribute. Specifically, given an attribute X_j , the set of census tracts $\{1, \dots, N\}$

is partitioned into a sensitive group S and a complementary non-sensitive group \bar{S} using the median value of X_j as threshold:

$$S = \{i : X_j(i) \geq \text{median}(X_j)\}, \quad \bar{S} = \{i : X_j(i) < \text{median}(X_j)\}.$$

Let y_1, \dots, y_N denote the accessibility values associated with each census tract, corresponding to the selected minimum, average, or maximum walking-distance measure. The average accessibility values for the sensitive and non-sensitive groups are defined as

$$\bar{y}_S = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{i \in S} y_i, \quad \bar{y}_{\bar{S}} = \frac{1}{|\bar{S}|} \sum_{i \in \bar{S}} y_i.$$

Accessibility disparity between both groups is then quantified through the relative difference

$$\frac{\max\{\bar{y}_S, \bar{y}_{\bar{S}}\} - \min\{\bar{y}_S, \bar{y}_{\bar{S}}\}}{\min\{\bar{y}_S, \bar{y}_{\bar{S}}\}}. \quad (1)$$

Indicator (1) therefore provides an interpretable measure of relative accessibility disparity between census tracts characterized by different socioeconomic conditions.

As will be shown in the next section, UrbanIneq automatically computes these exploratory disparity measures for all socioeconomic attributes integrated within the framework, allowing users to analyze accessibility disparities associated with different definitions of socioeconomic sensitivity. In addition to the numerical summaries, the platform generates spatial visualization outputs including accessibility maps and representations of the selected socioeconomic attribute, facilitating the joint exploration of accessibility conditions and potential inequality patterns.

4. Case studies

This section presents two illustrative case studies aimed at demonstrating the capabilities of UrbanIneq for exploring urban accessibility disparities across Andalusian municipalities. Both examples are conducted in municipalities located within the province of Cádiz, one of

the eight provinces of the Andalusian autonomous region in southern Spain. The first case study analyzes accessibility to Urban Green Spaces (UGS) in the city of Cádiz (the provincial capital), while the second examines accessibility to Healthcare Facilities (HCFs) in Jerez de la Frontera, considering both public and private healthcare services.

The objective of these examples is not to provide urban-policy assessments, but rather to illustrate how the framework can be used to integrate socioeconomic attributes, accessibility indicators, and spatial visualization outputs in order to identify potential inequality patterns. For illustrative consistency, the analyses presented in both case studies are based on the average walking-distance accessibility indicator.

4.1. Accessibility to urban green spaces in Cádiz

Cádiz is a medium-sized coastal city located in southwestern Spain, within the Andalusian region. The municipality has approximately 100,000 inhabitants distributed across $N = 106$ census tracts exhibiting heterogeneous socioeconomic conditions across urban neighborhoods. In this work, Cádiz serves as an illustrative example for analyzing accessibility to Urban Green Spaces (UGS) using the UrbanIneq platform. For the analyses presented in this section, one sparsely populated census tract associated with a predominantly industrial area was excluded from the accessibility computations in order to focus the analysis on residential urban environments. The corresponding configuration command is provided in Appendix C.2.

Figure 5 illustrates the spatial distribution of publicly accessible UGS across the municipality.

Table 1 summarizes the exploratory accessibility disparity measures obtained for the seven socioeconomic attributes considered by UrbanIneq. For each attribute, census tracts are divided according to the sample median into a group with attribute values above the median and a complementary group below the median. The columns “Avg. distance (above median)” and “Avg. distance (below median)” therefore correspond to the average accessibility values \bar{y}_S and $\bar{y}_{\bar{S}}$ associated with both groups, respectively. The last column reports the relative accessibility disparity computed with respect to the minimum of the two average accessibility

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of Urban Green Spaces (UGS) in Cádiz.

values.

The results reveal noticeable variability in the relative accessibility differences associated with different socioeconomic dimensions. In particular, the largest disparities are observed for the foreign-population attribute (X_6), the unemployment-rate attribute (X_5), and the loneliness index (X_7).

Attribute	Sample median	Avg. distance (above median)	Avg. distance (below median)	Rel. difference (%)
X_1 (Population)	993	2153.19	2151.99	0.06
X_2 (Income)	12651	2123.59	2181.59	2.73
X_3 (Prop. children)	14.32	2082.61	2222.57	6.72
X_4 (Prop. elderly)	24.57	2019.95	2285.23	13.13
X_5 (Unemployment rate)	27.33	2304.57	2000.61	15.19
X_6 (Prop. foreign)	1.94	2427.53	1877.65	29.29
X_7 (Loneliness index)	46.40	2285.97	2014.08	13.50

Table 1: Accessibility disparity summary for Cádiz based on the average walking-distance indicator to UGS.

One of the main socioeconomic challenges affecting both the city of Cádiz and the surrounding province is the relatively high unemployment rate. In particular, Table 1 indicates that census tracts with unemployment rates above the sample median exhibit average walking distances to Urban Green Spaces approximately 15.19% higher than those observed for census tracts below the median unemployment level. In this context, the unemployment attribute (X_5) could potentially be regarded as a sensitive attribute for subsequent accessibility-disparity or fairness-oriented analyses.

Figure 6 presents the spatial outputs generated by UrbanIneq for the selected analysis. The first map shows the average walking-distance accessibility surface to UGS across census tracts, where darker red tones indicate larger walking distances and therefore less favourable accessibility conditions. The second map represents the spatial distribution of the unemployment-rate attribute (X_5), with darker tones corresponding to census tracts exhibiting higher unemployment levels. The visual comparison between both layers facilitates the exploratory identification of potential accessibility disparities associated with unemployment patterns across the municipality.

Figure 6: Spatial outputs generated by UrbanIneq for the Cádiz UGS accessibility analysis.

4.2. Accessibility to healthcare facilities in Jerez de la Frontera

Jerez de la Frontera is one of the largest municipalities in Andalusia, located in the province of Cádiz in southwestern Spain. The municipality has approximately 210,000 inhabitants distributed across a spatially heterogeneous urban area composed of both compact urban neighborhoods and extensive peripheral zones. In this second illustrative example, UrbanIneq is used to explore accessibility patterns associated with Healthcare Facilities (HCFs), considering both public and private healthcare centers. For the analyses presented in this section, the census-tract exclusion procedure described in Section 2.2.3 is applied in order to remove peripheral industrial and sparsely populated areas from the accessibility computations, see Appendix C.2.

Figure 7 illustrates the spatial distribution of public and private healthcare centers across the municipality.

Table 2 reports the exploratory accessibility disparity measures associated with the seven

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of Healthcare facilities (HCF) in Jerez de la Frontera.

socioeconomic attributes considered for Jerez de la Frontera. In this illustrative example, the proportion of children (X_3) could be interpreted as a potential sensitive attribute, given that census tracts with child-population proportions above the sample median exhibit average walking distances to Healthcare Facilities (HCFs) approximately 14.47% higher than those observed for census tracts below the median.

Attribute	Sample median	Avg. distance		Rel. difference (%)
		(above median)	(below median)	
X_1 (Population)	1215	3011.71	2830.34	6.41
X_2 (Income)	9966	2786.92	3058.22	9.73
X_3 (Prop. children)	16.80	3117.34	2723.28	14.47
X_4 (Prop. elderly)	19.47	2728.69	3117.24	14.24
X_5 (Unemployment rate)	31.07	2861.40	2984.40	4.3
X_6 (Prop. foreign)	2.69	2624	3223.37	22.84
X_7 (Loneliness index)	44.4	2745.53	3105.11	13.10

Table 2: Accessibility disparity summary for Jerez de la Frontera based on the average walking-distance indicator to HCF.

Finally, Figure 8 illustrates the spatial outputs associated with the HCF accessibility example in Jerez de la Frontera. The first map represents the average walking-distance accessibility values to HCFs across census tracts, where darker tones correspond to less favourable accessibility conditions. The second map displays the spatial distribution of the child-population attribute (X_3), with darker tones indicating census tracts characterized by higher proportions of children. In particular, several northeastern sectors of the municipality simultaneously exhibit comparatively high distance values together with elevated child-population levels, suggesting the presence of potentially less favourable accessibility conditions affecting younger population groups in those areas.

Figure 8: Spatial outputs generated by UrbanIneq for the Jerez de la Frontera HCF accessibility analysis.

5. Conclusions and future work

UrbanIneq provides an open and reproducible framework for transforming heterogeneous public urban data into harmonized census-tract accessibility datasets. By integrating socio-economic indicators, spatial information, routing services, and accessibility measures through

a single workflow, the framework reduces much of the technical effort typically required to conduct urban accessibility analyses using multiple institutional data sources.

One of the main contributions of UrbanIneq lies in the generation of openly accessible urban datasets enriched with potential socio-spatial inequality patterns. In addition to accessibility indicators associated with Urban Green Spaces (UGS) and Healthcare Facilities (HCFs), the framework incorporates socioeconomic attributes that may support exploratory disparity analyses and future fairness-oriented research in spatial contexts. The examples presented in this paper illustrate how UrbanIneq can support the joint exploration of accessibility conditions, socioeconomic characteristics, and spatial disparities through tract-level datasets, summary indicators, and visualization outputs.

Nevertheless, several limitations should be acknowledged. The current implementation is restricted to the 785 municipalities of Andalusia, and extending the framework to other national or international contexts would require adapting the underlying data sources and administrative structures. Accessibility indicators are currently computed using pedestrian-network distances only, without considering multimodal transportation systems or temporal mobility dynamics. Moreover, the accessibility indicators currently implemented in UrbanIneq capture only part of the complexity of real urban accessibility conditions. Minimum-distance indicators may overestimate accessibility when only small or low-quality facilities are nearby, whereas average-distance measures may have weaker behavioural interpretation since residents do not interact equally with all destinations within a city. In addition, the current version of the framework is based on datasets associated with the 2021 reference year. Although this common temporal reference facilitates harmonization across data sources, it does not capture more recent demographic, socioeconomic, or urban transformations.

Future developments of UrbanIneq will focus on extending both the territorial coverage and the methodological capabilities of the framework. Planned extensions include the incorporation of additional Spanish regions, temporal analyses across multiple years and travel-time accessibility indicators. Altogether, these extensions would further strengthen the

utility of UrbanIneq as an open infrastructure for urban accessibility analysis and socio-spatial inequality research.

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Data and code availability

The UrbanIneq platform, together with all reproducibility materials associated with this work, is publicly available at <https://github.com/JoseCarlos1611/UrbanIneq>. Unless otherwise stated, all results presented in this paper were generated using Release v1.0.

Appendix A. Analysis configuration examples

UrbanIneq allows users to customize accessibility analyses through configuration parameters and API options. In particular:

- **TRACT_FIX**: specifies optional centroid adjustments.
- **TRACT_EXCLUDE**: defines census tracts excluded from the analysis.
- **LOCATIONS**: selects the category of urban services or points of interest.
- **DIST_TYPE**: specifies the accessibility aggregation measure.

- **BIASVAR**: selects the socioeconomic attribute used for disparity visualization or analysis.

For example, centroid adjustments for selected census tracts in Seville (see Section 2.2) can be specified as follows:

```
R> TRACT_FIX <- list("4109111001" = c(233782.9, 4139657.6),
                    "4109107013" = c(235737.2, 4145047.4),
                    "4109107022" = c(239105.8, 4147356.0),
                    "4109107023" = c(242366.0, 4146947.5),
                    "4109109069" = c(242164.7, 4144100.2),
                    "4109109018" = c(242929.5, 4141649.7),
                    "4109105051" = c(238157.2, 4139082.9))
```

Similarly, selected census tracts in Jerez de la Frontera were excluded from the accessibility analysis (see Section 2.2 and Section 4.2) through:

```
R> TRACT_EXCLUDE <- c("1102010001", "1102010002", "1102004003",
                     "1102008001", "1102009002", "1102009004",
                     "1102009005", "1102009006", "1102009007",
                     "1102009008", "1102009009", "1102009010",
                     "1102009011", "1102009012", "1102009013",
                     "1102009014", "1102010003", "1102010004")
```

Finally, in the case of Cádiz (see Section 4.1), one peripheral census tract corresponding to a predominantly industrial and sparsely populated area was excluded from the accessibility analysis through:

```
R> TRACT_EXCLUDE <- c("1101210012")
```

Appendix B. Structure of the generated UrbanIneq datasets

For each municipality, UrbanIneq generates an R object stored in RDS format. The resulting dataset integrates the socioeconomic attributes, the accessibility indicators, and

spatial information required for subsequent statistical and geospatial analyses. File names are identified using the official five-digit municipality code defined by the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE).

Let N denote the number of census tracts within the selected municipality and $p = 7$ the number of socioeconomic attributes integrated by the platform. Then, the generated R object contains the following components.

x: An $N \times (p + 1)$ data frame containing the values of the attributes X_1, \dots, X_7 associated with the N census tracts of the municipality, including an intercept column.

xnorm: A standardized version of **x**.

y: An $N \times 1$ vector containing the accessibility values associated with each census tract.

geometry: A polygon layer containing the spatial boundaries of census tracts within the municipality.

raw: A consolidated spatial dataset integrating predictor variables, accessibility values, and tract geometries.

gz: A polygon layer containing the geometries of Urban Green Spaces (UGS).

clinics_any: A point layer containing all Healthcare Facilities (HCFs) located within the municipality.

clinics_public: A point layer containing only public Healthcare Facilities (HCFs).

name: The municipality name.

centroids: An $N \times 2$ matrix containing the coordinates of census-tract centroids.

d: An $N \times N$ Euclidean distance matrix computed between census-tract centroids.

Several components of the generated dataset are specifically intended to facilitate subsequent spatial statistical and predictive modeling analyses. In particular, the standardized predictor matrix (**xnorm**), the inclusion of an intercept column within **x**, and the Euclidean distance matrix (**d**) are designed to support spatial regression modeling approaches commonly used in urban analytics and spatial data science.

Appendix C. Quick deployment

UrbanIneq can be deployed through Docker Compose using the following commands:

```
git clone https://github.com/JoseCarlos1611/UrbanIneq.git
cd UrbanIneq
docker-compose up --build
```

The services initialize automatically in dependency order. Once the deployment process is completed, the frontend interface becomes accessible through the local web server.

Appendix D. Technical implementation details

UrbanIneq is implemented as a Docker-based microservices architecture composed of four independent services communicating through HTTP requests.

OSRM routing service

The routing engine is based on the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) configured for pedestrian routing over the Andalusian OpenStreetMap extract. The service runs within a dedicated Docker container and exposes routing services through port 5001.

R/Plumber geospatial processing service

Geospatial processing tasks are implemented in R and exposed through a Plumber API running on port 8000. This service performs data retrieval, preprocessing, accessibility computation, spatial integration, and output generation. The main API endpoints include:

- GET /health: service health verification.
- GET /bias-table/<city_code>: retrieval of disparity summaries for a selected municipality.
- POST /run: execution of the complete UrbanIneq workflow.
- POST /inspect-rds: inspection of generated RDS datasets.

During initialization, the service verifies the availability of required datasets and downloads missing resources when necessary.

FastAPI orchestration layer

The FastAPI gateway runs on port 8080 and coordinates communication between the frontend, the routing engine, and the R processing service. This layer manages municipality resolution, workflow execution, job monitoring, result aggregation, and output delivery.

Complete API documentation and endpoint specifications are available through the interactive FastAPI/OpenAPI interface distributed with the platform.

React frontend

The frontend interface, implemented using React, TypeScript, Vite, and Tailwind CSS, runs on port 8081. The interface supports municipality selection, parameter configuration, job execution, accessibility visualization, output download, and history management.

Table D.3 summarizes the main software dependencies and infrastructure requirements of UrbanIneq.

Component	Main tools	Purpose
R environment	R, <code>sf</code> , <code>osrm</code> , <code>readxl</code> , <code>ggplot2</code> , <code>plumber</code>	Geospatial processing, routing integration, visualization, and API services
Python environ- ment	Python, FastAPI, Uvi- corn, Pydantic	Workflow orchestration, API management, and inter-service communication
Frontend	React, TypeScript, Vite, Tailwind CSS	Interactive visualization and user interac- tion
Infrastructure	Docker, Docker Com- pose	Containerized deployment and repro- ducibility

Table D.3: Main software dependencies and infrastructure components used by UrbanIneq.

Additional implementation resources, source code, and deployment materials are available in the UrbanIneq framework repository.

Appendix E. Internal processing modules and workflow implementation

UrbanIneq organizes its internal workflow into a set of modular R scripts responsible for data retrieval, preprocessing, spatial analysis, inequality computation, and output generation.

Data retrieval

The `dataId.R` module manages the download and organization of institutional and OpenStreetMap-based datasets, including census boundaries, demographic indicators, Urban Green Spaces (UGS), Healthcare Facilities (HCF), and street-network information.

Numerical data preprocessing

The `numdata.R` module performs preprocessing and harmonization of socioeconomic variables, including attribute selection, standardization, and construction of the numerical components used in the final datasets.

Spatial processing and accessibility computation

The `spdata.R` module implements the spatial analysis workflow, including centroid generation, tract filtering, spatial joins, and accessibility calculations using the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM). This stage computes minimum, average, and maximum walking-distance indicators associated with UGS and HCF accessibility.

Accessibility disparity analysis

The `inequalities.R` module computes accessibility disparity summaries based on the sensitive attributes integrated within the platform. Census tracts are partitioned into sensitive (S) and non-sensitive (\bar{S}) groups according to the median value of the selected socioeconomic attribute, enabling comparative accessibility analyses between population groups.

Output generation and visualization

The `outputData.R` module assembles the final RDS datasets and generates companion outputs including accessibility maps, spatial layers, ZIP archives, and metadata associated with the executed analysis workflow.

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